

Influence of video delay on quality, presence, and sickness in viewport adaptive omnidirectional streaming

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Abstract—Current extended reality (XR) applications use omnidirectional video to help users immersion in order to feel presence. However, distributed reality requires the access to distant video sources that cannot be instantaneously delivered. Thus, this delay becomes a key problem in omnidirectional video streaming where user actions cannot be simultaneously matched by system reactions. So, we have designed and executed an experiment to evaluate the influence of this delay on the quality of experience, the sense of presence, and the simulator sickness caused. To do it, we have developed a viewport adaptive simulator to render simultaneously two layers of immersive video to allow different viewport adaptive schemes and different delays. Four adaptation schemes have been considered for the integration of video acquired from remote pan-tilt-zoom (PTZ) cameras: PTZ video alone, PTZ video over static preregistered panorama, PTZ over low quality 360VR video, and tile-based 360VR video. Two delay conditions have been considered for short (up to 300 ms) and long (over 500 ms) values. Nine source clips have been extracted from three different video sources and processed for each scheme and delay to generate 180 clips. Twenty observers have assessed them delivering quality scores for each clips and presence and sickness values for each source, adaptation, and delay conditions. The analysis shows a clear influence of the delay condition and the adaptation scheme on the perceived quality. Moreover, the analysis shows that the considered adaptation schemes and delay conditions have a small influence on the sense of presence and little effect on observers sickness.

Index Terms—Video delay, Quality of experience, Presence, Sickness, Extended reality

I. INTRODUCTION

Telepresence and distributed reality requires of distant video sources. As in the extended reality applications, the immersive video can be used for enhancing the sense of being there and thus, the telepresence environments. Furthermore, some application of telepresence such as remote conference, video surveillance and remote operation require of real-time video streaming.

For recording the environment, telepresence systems usually works with Pan Tilt Zom (PTZ) cameras due to its capacity for moving its angle of vision. However, schemes of immersive video using PTZ cameras in telepresence environments keeps unexplored. Some telepresence environments already use the

PTZ cameras. Thus, it is reasonable to explore the use PTZ cameras for recording immersive video to enhance the telepresence. The classic methods of immersive video delivery send the entire scene to the devices using 360 cameras. However, using PTZ cameras for capturing a 360 environment only the camera view is being transmitted while the rest of the 360 scene is not updated.

A similar scheme of immersive video with 360 cameras is the Tile-Based encoding. In this scheme, only a portion of the video is sent at a high quality while the rest of the 360 scene is coded at minor quality. When the user moves to another position, the high quality region is updated. [1]

All these schemes are classified as viewport adaptive schemes. The viewport adaptative schemes for immersive video streaming shares the same problem, the delay.

The delay is an important parameter for QoE in immersive environments. The increase of the end-to-end latency may drive into unpleasant experiences [2]. Hence, the impact of delay in different schemes of adaptive viewport immersive video streaming in terms of Quality of Experience (QoE) is presented in this paper.

The state of the art talks about the subjective assessment for measure the user's QoE and his immersion. [3]–[5]. Subjective factors such as sense of presence, cybersickness [6] and main opinion score are claimed to be a good method for measuring the QoE of immersive video [1], [2], [5], [7], [8]. In this paper, we will measure the impact of the delay in terms of QoE. Therefore, video quality, sense of presence and sickness questionnaires will be done. For the video quality, DCR will be used. Then, by using this score for the video quality, the results will be the main opinion score of the experience. Additionally, the sense of presence and the sickness are key factors for measuring the QoE in immersive environments [5]. Furthermore, for measuring the presence and the sickness factors, mini-MEC [9] and Simulator sickness Questionnaires questionnaire [6] will be used.

Recent works have measured the impact of network delay in the QoE in immersive video delivery [1], [7], [10]. However, some extra delays must be taken into account in telepresence

environments as a consequence of the real-time streaming. Furthermore, PTZ video transmission schemes add an extra 200 ms because the intrinsic mechanical delay of the cameras [10].

In this paper we have measured the QoE in four types of schemes based on the viewport adaptation schemes of tile-based videos and immersive PTZ video delivery:

- Foveated imaging [11].
- Tile-Based 360 video.
- PTZ video delivery.
- PTZ video delivery over preregistered background.

All these scenarios will be simulated using the tool developed for this experiment. The common idea is to generate a scene where the user is watching a 360 video with a high quality at first. After that, the user will be freely to move around the 360 scene. Then, in each scenario the effect of the added delay will cause different video situations. The purpose of this experiment is to compare the different schemes of adaptation with a variety of delay scenarios in terms of QoE using subjective questionnaires. In this paper we present:

- A novelty scheme for adaptive video schemes
- A tool for simulate configuration in terms of delay, FOV and tile distribution of different schemes of adaptive immersive video.
- A tool for measuring QoE over different transmission schemes involving PTZ immersive and tile-based video

II. VIEW-PORT ADAPTIVE SIMULATOR

We have developed a specific tool using the Unity3D engine to carry out the experiment. This tool supersedes a previous subjective assessment tool XXXXX¹, also developed using the Unity3D engine, by allowing the simultaneous play of two overlaid 360 videos to simulate different types of viewport adaptive immersive video schemes with various delay conditions. Thus, different delay values can be used to simulate the end-to-end latency between a movement of the user (an action) and the instant when he can see again high quality video (a reaction).

A. Tool design

The main requisite for the design of the tool has been the ability to render two different virtual spheres as can be seen in Figure 1. This is an horizontal cross-section of the virtual spheres viewed from above.

The higher resolution video is rendered in the inner sphere (circular sector in Table), but the lower resolution video is rendered in the outer sphere (circle in Figure). As the user can only see what happens within the Field of View (FOV), it could happen that only a fraction of the high quality video lays within the viewing zone. Thus, the image on the inner sphere will be cropped and will occupy only a fraction of the FOV. The solid and dashed lines in Figure 1 respectively represent the situation before and after a left turn of the user's head.

Fig. 1. Top-view diagram of user movement

However, according to the design, this situation will vanish as new high resolution video covers the FOV after some delay.

The tool is able to simulate two ways of 360 video scenario. On the one hand, the tool can simulate a 360 video tile-based encoded. On the other hand, the tool can also simulate a 360 foveated video captured with PTZ cameras. So, several parameters can be configured, such as: the FOV, the end-to-end latency, the number of tiles, and the custom questionnaires after each scenario and sequence.

There is only one video rendered in the inner sphere for both PTZ and PTZ over preregistered background viewport adaptation schemes. So, there are two alternative initial configurations for this scenario. Either the outer sphere is filled with a blank texture or it is filled with the preregistered background, equivalent to the first frame of the 360 video. Later, as said before, the user, after any movement, can only see a fraction of the 360 video. Nevertheless, each PTZ video frame updates its corresponding position in the outer sphere. Therefore, this procedure allows an updated of the background that will be rendered when the user looks again to that previous position. Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the FOV at sometime after the beginning of the session.

Fig. 2. PTZ viewport adaption

On the other hand, two videos are rendered for the foveated imaging and the tile-based viewport adaptation schemes. Thus, in these cases, the user will be watching the lower resolution video rendered on the outer sphere, as Figure 4 shows, while

¹Reference removed to preserve double-blind

Fig. 3. PTZ over preregistered background viewport adaption

the transition period occurs. The tool can be configured in two ways for this scenario: the tiles are placed at fixed positions (Tile-based) or the tiles follow the user's orientation continuously (Foveated imaging).

Fig. 4. Tile-based viewport adaption

B. Delay

The delay associated to the delivery of immersive video streaming is an key parameter for achieving and maintaining the users' immersion. To analyze the end-to-end delay in our viewport adaptation schemes, we consider the following elementary delays:

- τ_{pos} : Position: time required to send the position of the viewing device to the camera.
- τ_{adj} : Adjust position: mechanical delay of the PTZ cameras.
- τ_{cod} : Acquisition: capturing, local processing like stitching, and encoding.
- τ_{net} : Network: one-way transmission delay.
- τ_{dec} : Rendering: decoding and rendering.

Fig. 5. Real-time immersive video streaming diagram

Figure 5 shows the elements of a real-time immersive video streaming system controlled by the user movement. Firstly, the video engine sends the new position to the camera adding τ_{pos} , which is similar to τ_{net} . Then, if the camera is a PTZ, it will require a certain time to move to the new position τ_{adj} . This delay does not exist for 360 video cameras. The video is acquired by the camera and τ_{cod} includes the capturing, the local processing, and the encoding of the video. Currently, only 360 cameras require stitching. Then, the video is delivered over the network to the video engine requiring $2*\tau_{net}$. Finally, the video is decoded and rendered to the viewing device adding τ_{dec} .

All these delays can be grouped into an overall value equal to the latency between a movement of the user and the instant when he can see again high quality video as Equation 1 shows.

$$\tau_{e2e} = \tau_{pos} + \tau_{adj} + \tau_{cod} + \tau_{net} + \tau_{dec} \approx \tau_{adj} + \tau_{cod} + 2*\tau_{net} + \tau_{dec} \quad (1)$$

Our viewport adaptive simulator considers the overall delay value as a design parameter. Different simulations will involve several sets of delay alternatives. Our tool is able to cope with them.

C. Sources

The simulator has been designed to accurately emulate the two cameras considered: PTZ and 360 omnidirectional. To be able to conduct a fair comparison between them, source contents at two different resolutions (named high and low) should be available in principle. However, as said before, we wish to avoid any implementation issues not related to the analysis of the viewport adaptation schemes. Therefore, we have considered high quality equirectangular video sources from which we can obtain two different versions: a fraction of the frame at the same original quality to emulate PTZ cameras and a full frame at reduced quality to emulate 360 cameras. Although, the simulator can deal more resolution levels, only two qualities have been considered here. Moreover, there is a large difference between them to help discriminate the results. So, the high quality has a resolution of 4096x1980 and the low quality another of 420x320.

Three different video sources have been considered:

- Moving camera: video of a drone flying over a seaport.
- Fixed camera: fixed drone recording a medical assistance.
- Exploring videos: a flamenco classroom.

D. Subjective Quality Assessment

The purpose of the experiment is to measure the QoE while varying the conditions of delay and/or adaptation schemes. Playlists and questionnaires for subjective quality assessment are managed by a new tool based on a previous subjective assessment tool XXXXX². This tool provides a Unity3D compatible environment for:

- Elaborate custom questionnaires.

²Reference removed to preserve double-blind

- Create randomized playlists following the recommendations of ITU-T P.360-VR.
- Sample and record the gaze of the users.
- Record the scores of the users.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This section explains how the tool has been configured for evaluating the QoE of different schemes of adaptive immersive video transmission. Specifically, this section gives details about the video sequences, subjective questionnaires, delays, FoVs, devices and the experimental scheme used in this experiment.

A. Subjective Questionnaires

In this experiment, quality, presence and dizziness questionnaires were used to assess QoE. As the user always start with high quality, we have used the Degradation Category Rating (DCR) of the P.910 [12] to measure video quality. As DCR is designed for evaluating the degradation between a pair of scenes, we have requested, in this case, users to assess how unpleasant the effect of the delay in each sequence was. Following the ITU-T Rec. P.910 [12], differential score opinions are computed and, to do so, a hidden reference, absence of end-to-end delay, was presented randomly to the subjects.

To measure presence, the mini-MEC test, is a sub-sampling of the MEC questionnaire, was used [9] [13]. Only certain questions about attention allocation, spatial stimulation, self-location, possible actions cognitive involvement and suspension disbelief were asked.

TABLE I
MINI-MEC QUESTIONS

Question	Factor
I devoted my whole attention to the video.	Attention Allocation
I was able to imagine the arrangement of the spaces presented in the video very well.	Spatial Situation
I felt like I was actually there in the environment of the presentation.	Self-Location
The video presentation activated my thinking	Cognitive Involvement
I had the impression that i could be active in the environment of the presentation.	Possible Actions
I did not really pay attention to the existence of errors or inconsistencies in the video.	Suspension of Disbelief

To measure dizziness, two different questionnaires were used at different stages of the experiment. On the one hand, the tool presented a question about sickness at the end of each sequence [8] "How is the level of dizziness or nausea?". On the other hand, before the experiment start and after each part of the session, the SSQ [6] was asked.

B. Devices

The Head-Mounted Display (HMD) Lenovo Mirage Solo as a player device was used in the experiment. This device has a display of 5.5" with an IPS panel and a resolution of 2560x1440 pixels. It has an FoV of 110 degrees.

C. Video Tiling and FoV schemes

Adaptive immersive video transmission is simulated in the experiment. The fraction of the high quality 360 video that is being watched is defined by the FoV. Horizontal FoV was fixed at 110 and the Vertical FoV was fixed at 180.

D. Chosen Delays

The overall end-to-end latency groups all kind of delays as described in a previous subsection. Related work in the evaluation of the impact of streaming delay in immersive video have used delays between 100ms and one second [10] [14]. Thus, we have considered two groups of delay in our experiment, short and long ones, as shown in Table II.

TABLE II
DELAY GROUPS

Group	Reference	Delay 1	Delay 2
Long	0 ms	150 ms	300 ms
Short	0 ms	500 ms	1000 ms

E. Workflow

The experiment was done using 20 participants with an age range between 22 and 40.

In a training session previous to the test, the four adaptation schemes were shown continuously with the highest delay. After each scheme, the user scored the DCR. Therefore, the user can get used to the delay effects and the voting method. After this training session the experiment was performed following the diagram of Figure 6.

Before starting the experiment, each user answers the SSQ to gather information about his/her initial sickness state. At the beginning, a delay group (short or long) is chosen for the first session. After that, a sequence and an adaptive scheme is randomly selected. Each sequence is divided in three 20 second cuts. Each cut is played using the selected adaptive scheme, and each one with a different latency value from the selected delay group. After each cut, DCR is scored. When the sequence has been played, the user scores his/her presence and sickness levels. After all 12 sequences have been played, the user answers the full SSQ again. Then, after a 10-minute rest period, the whole process is repeated with the other delay group.

IV. RESULTS

A. Video Quality

Figure 7 shows the MOS and 95% confidence interval of the the DCR scores for the different adaptation schemes and delays. In all cases, there is a strong dependency between the delay and the DMOS. It is worth noting that even the relatively low delay of 150 ms is clearly perceptible. The slope of the curves decreases faster between 150 and 300 milliseconds with the increase of the delay. However, the scores decrease lower between the 300 milliseconds and the second. This situation shows that the end-to-end delay is specially relevant in the first hundreds of milliseconds of delay.

Fig. 6. Test diagram

Figure 7 also shows how the PTZ scheme is significantly worse than the rest of the schemes. It is specially interesting to compare it with the PTZ over preregistered background scheme: adding any kind of 360 information to the PTZ video, either a static frame or a low-resolution video, significantly enhances video quality scores. Moreover, PTZ over preregistered background scheme shows similar results than 360 camera based schemes.

A 2-way ANOVA was done to check the dependency of the DMOS results on the adaptation scheme (AS) and the source (SRC), whose results are shown in Table III. As previously seen, a significant effect on the adaptation scheme was found ($F_{3,1460} = 7.40, p < 0.001$), but no significant dependency was found on the individual source sequences or the interaction of both conditions ($p > 0.05$). This result supports our decision of aggregating scores from different sources in the analysis of the results.

Fig. 7. DMOS score for each scheme

B. Sense of Presence

Figure 8 shows the mini-MEC presence score for each adaptive scheme and delay group. Unlike video quality scores, there is no significant difference between adaptation schemes or delay groups. Under the conditions of our experiment (visible

Fig. 8. Mini-MEC score for scheme and delay group

Fig. 9. Average of mini-MEC questionnaire for each item

Fig. 10. Simulator sickness question average for scheme and delay group

TABLE III
2-WAY ANOVA OF THE DMOS

Anova	S.S.	d.f.	F	p-value	η^2
AS	41.42	3	7.40	6.4×10^{-5}	0.015
SRC	9.31	2	2.49	0.08	0.003
AS x SRC	12.47	6	1.11	0.35	0.005
Residual	2724.11	1460			

TABLE IV
SIMULATE SICKNESS QUESTIONNAIRE AVERAGE RESULTS

	O	N	D	σ	Total Score
Starting	15.17	15.92	7.33	7.33	11.02 \pm 8.10
Resting	37.11	33.43	15.56	24.77	23.86 \pm 10.85
Ending	50.66	43.51	20.68	32.43	31.73 \pm 14.21

effect of the adaptation with respect to an homogeneous no-delay scenario), there is no influence of the specific delay or adaptation scheme on the sense of presence.

Figure 9 illustrates the scores for each mini-MEC item for each delay group and scheme. There are significant differences between the different individual factors that influence on spatial presence but, for each of them, there is no influence of delay or scheme either.

C. Sickness

Figure 10 illustrates the mean value of the sickness question for scheme and delay group. As in the sense of presence, there is no significant difference between the schemes or the delays.

Table IV shows the average results of the SSQ Nausea (N), Disorientation (D) and Oculomotor (O) factors aside from his total score with the confidence interval for 95% confidence [6]. An increase of sickness over time is observed, in line with similar experiments of visualization of 360 videos with HMDs [15].

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an experiment has been designed for measuring QoE of different adaptive schemes for omnidirectional video streaming using different end-to-end delays. The experiment measures the subjective video quality, the sense of presence and the sickness. The adaptive schemes evaluated use different camera systems: PTZ and/or 360 Cameras. The measurement of the video quality shows that the PTZ scheme is significantly worse than PTZ over preregistered background, Foveated imaging and tile-based schemes. The results show that adding 360 information to a PTZ adaptive scheme enhances the perceived quality of the experience.

For the considered adaptation strategies, the relationship between video quality and end-to-end delay has been analyzed (Figure 7). Between 500 and 1000 ms of delay the video quality decreases slower than between 150 and 500 ms in all schemes. In particular, the curve for Tile-based adaptations can be considered as a lower bound for quality degradation as

a function of end-to-end delay in viewport-adaptive streaming scenarios.

Under the conditions of the experiment, it has been shown that the level of delay or the selection of a specific adaptation scheme have no influence on the sense of presence or the simulator sickness. Even strong foveation schemes (such as PTZ) and large delays can be used without significantly impair the sense of presence, which supports the possibility of using PTZ cameras within Virtual Reality setups. Further research should be done to compare these results with schemes where the low quality image is not so easily perceived, e.g. with higher-quality background video or lower delays.

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